

KUTUMBAKAM IN KHASI FOLK NARRATIVES: A KHASI ECOSOPHY

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Abstract

The Khasis are one of the three main tribes in Meghalaya. They follow matrilineal system. Owing to their oral tradition they never had their own script until the year 1841 when Thomas Jones, the Welsh Missionary, arrived. He introduced them the Roman script. Therefore, many of the folk narratives have been documented only after writing was introduced. The first folk narrative that was documented by U Rabon Singh however, is only as old as one hundred and fifteen years. Khasi Folk narratives comprise of myths, legends and folktales. They encapsulate the culture of the community. They are reservoir from which are drawn their worldview, philosophy and identity. Owing its origin to a matrilineal tribe, these narratives reflect the sense of inclusivity. The attitude of care and concern is shown towards non-humans also. This paper presents the following argument: The Khasis worldview is similar to the Sanskrit term 'Kutumbakam' which means 'the world is one family'; interconnectedness of every being is significant for the Khasis to reach their self-realization; the sense of seeing the inherent worth of every being is due to the tenet 'Ka Tip-Briew Ka Tip-Blei' or 'To know man-to know god'. Although, the current scenario, in the name of development, human chauvinism and speciesism have crept in, yet the narratives can act as a power house that preserves the cohesion between humans and non-humans.

Key word: Khasi, Ecosophy, Hynniew Trep, Kutumbakam, Weretigers, U Blei.

Meghalaya is one of the eight states in North-East India. It shares its boundary with Assam in the North and East, and with an international State, Bangladesh, in the West and South. Meghalaya, which means 'the abode of clouds', is the home of two tribes; the Khasis and Jaintias, also known as the *Hynniew Trep- Hynniew Skum*, and the Garos. These two tribes follow matrilineal system.

The origin of the Khasi tribe is inconclusive as there is no written document that reflects it. Many scientific researchers have theorised but vary in opinions. Some opine that the Khasis came from South East Asia. Some believe that they came from Myanmar. While others strongly believe that they are a part of the Mon-Khmer group of Cambodia (Kharbangar 8). Because of the disputed origin, the Khasis' common belief of origin is drawn from folk narratives such as myths, legends, folktales. Presently, the Khasis accept, undisputedly, that they are the descendants of the *Hynniew Trep – Hynniew Skum*. According to the myth, the *Hynniew Trep* are the seven clans which existed alongside *U Blei* or God in heaven with the other nine clans. *Ramew*, a guardian spirit of the earth, pleaded *U Blei* to send caretakers in order to preserve the beauty of the earth. *U Blei*, then, decreed that the *Hynniew Trep* descend on earth as its

caretakers. Hence, the myth has been a unifying force, drawing all the Khasis together under one umbrella.

The myth about the origin of the Khasis plays an important role in shaping their worldview. They regard themselves as sojourners on earth who have to go back to the abode of *U Blei* after their earthly life. They use the expression '*bam kwai ha dwar u Blei*' or 'to eat betel nut at the door of God's house' for a person who passed away, to remind themselves that their permanent place is with *U Blei*. They regard the earth as a gift from *U Blei* and to safeguard it according to the decree. They believe that the earth is guarded by the spirit *Ramew*. *Ramew* is a female entity whose husband, *Basa*, is the patron of villages. *Ramew* felt that her life was monotonous and therefore she prayed to *U Blei* to bless her with children. *U Blei* listened to her prayers and gave her five children; *Sun*, *Moon*, *Wind*, *Water*, and *Fire*. These five siblings transformed the earth into a salubrious environment. *Ramew* who saw the transformation on earth wanted to preserve it and prayed again to *U Blei* for caretakers. When *U Blei* sent the *Hynniew Trep* as caretakers, He planted a divine tree *Ka Jingkieng Ksiar* or Golden Ladder, as a testament of His covenant with them, at *U Lum Sohpet Bneng* or the Hill of the Heaven's Navel that allowed them to descend and ascend heaven and earth. The divine tree *Ka Jingkieng Ksiar*

connects *U Sohpet Bneng* to the very throne of God, the Divine Decree and therefore the Khasis speak of the age of *U Sohpet Bneng* as the divine link between God and his creatures and so peace and harmony prevails all over the earth. There was no pap and man had direct intercourse with God. It was a time when man lived happily having free access both to heaven and to earth (Wolflang 49).

The opportunity of the *Hynniew Trep* to ascend and descend the *Jingkieng Ksiar* daily is a phase that enabled them to establish a connection with it. Besides serving as a link, the *Jingkieng Ksiar* is their power, happiness and identity. It is deep-seated in their psyche that the tree is a means of communication to *U Blei*. This experience made them confer value on every tree. They view forests as 'sacrosanct'. It is with this attitude that forests are treated with respect and patches of them are preserved. Preservation of forests is realised under three categories; *Law Lyngdoh* or Indigenous Priest Grove, *Lawniam* or the Indigenous faith Grove and *Law Kyntang* or the Sacred Grove. There are 79 groves as documented in Meghalaya. Out of which 32 are in East Khasi Hills, 13 in West Khasi Hills, 15 in Jaintia Hills, 8 in East Garo Hills, 8 in West Garo Hills and 3 in Ri Bhoi district (Shangpliang 30). Every Khasi behaves with utmost propriety when entering these groves. It is prohibited to cut a tree or pluck a leaf or even remove a stone from these groves. It is believed that whoever goes against these prohibitions will fall under the curse of the forest deity *U Ryngkew U Basa*. Preservation of forests is done also with a purpose that forests are the habitat of deities and weretigers. The Khasis believe that *U Ryngkew* reveals himself in the form of a tiger. Certain groves are set aside for him.

There are certain Khasi clans in and around the villages of *Pahambir* and *Pahamshken* in the northern part of the Khasi Hills of Meghalaya which could transform themselves into tigers. The men and women of such clans are known as *khla phuli*. 'Khla' is a Khasi word for tiger and 'phuli' means "a man who transforms into a tiger, who has five fingers and five toes. People can make out even by studying footprints whether the paw-marks belong to the four-clawed creature of the jungle or whether it is the phuli-tiger with five claws that has passed by" (Kharmawphlang 68).

The veneration of forests has been rightly acclaimed by a famous Khasi writer H.O Mawrie who says, "*U Khasi u im bad ka mariang, bad ka mariang ka im bad u*", which means "A Khasi lives with nature and nature with Khasi" (Shangpliang 28). The reverential attitude is a source to a customary practice of *iapan*. The claue of *iapan* is 'to request'. It is a concept that explains the nature of the Khasis when they need anything from the forest to tend to one's needs. Before they enter, they request the forest

Look here, for I have come to chop you, not because I hate or want to destroy you, but I really need you as it is bequeathed by the Divine Decree that I may fell you. So that you can as well partake in all my needs. So that you can be part of my family, be part of my garden. Therefore, allow me, obey, bend to my right so that I can chop you with my axe, for even though you will fall now yet your name and fame will grow, you will reach before the gods, before the kings, the great ones, the priest, the elders and all the people from one generation to the next. So that your seeds, your boughs, your trunk will creep, extend, grow in your abode here in the forest. Hei Ho! I have blessed. Hei Ho! God will bless, and you do forgive me. I have spoken (Nongkynrih 49).

Interestingly, the Khasis do not regard creations around them as mute and insensate. All creations have feelings and can communicate their emotions. For them stones, trees, birds, animals converse with human beings. There is an era, known as the Golden Age, when all creations on earth could converse peacefully amongst themselves. The proof of its existence is weaved in every Khasi folk narrative. The Khasis would start any folk narrative with the introduction 'in the days that were ancient, when the earth was tender, when men, beasts, stones and trees spoke as one'. The Khasis' inclusiveness of man, beasts, stones and trees is '*vasudaiv kutumbkam*'. The Sanskrit term *vasudaiv kutumbakam* means that the world is a family. S. Gurumurthy says, 'when we say '*vasudaiv kutumbkam*' it is not that we are comfortable with each other. We are comfortable with every living creation in the world' (00:00:19-29). No thing is an isolation and will survive thinking so. Everything is interconnected. The *Maha Upanishad* speaks about the interdependence of all things; *Ayam nijah paro veti ganana laghucetasam, Udaracharitanam tu vasudhaiva kutumbkam*. The transliteration of it is, 'this is mine, that is his, say the small minded. The wise believe that the entire world is a family (Vasudhaiv).

The Khasis believe that every creature is endowed with a spirit and they have sensation just like them. The chief trait that differentiates between other creatures and the Khasis is the intellect. The myth tells that when *U Blei* bestowed gifts to every creature the Khasis received the intellect as they are physically weak (Wolflang 17). Apart from the intellect, the Khasis are at par with all creatures. One of the equal treatments that is shown to every creature is the common usage of the same language for communication. The equality of treatment shown by the Khasis to all creatures is similar to the philosophy propagated by Arne Naess, Ecosophy T. Ecosophy is different from ecology. While ecology is a science that studies the relationship amongst living organisms, ecosophy is a philosophy of ecological harmony. Arne Naess himself explains, "Ecology is a limited science that makes use of scientific methods. Philosophy is the most general forum for debate on fundamentals, descriptive, as well perspective... By an Ecosophy I mean a philosophy of ecological harmony or equilibrium" (Callicott 237). Ecosophy T is the personal ecosophy of Arne Naess. The letter T stands for '*Tvergastein*', his mountain hut in Norway which literally means 'across the stones'. Arne Naess suggests that there are other possible ecosophies A, B, C, etc. But what is important is that each personal ecosophy should make an individual realise the need of caring for the well-being of the environment. He went beyond the popular ecological movement of the 1960s by identifying the inherent worth of each being in the environment. He opines that every human being must be mindful that his/her identity is developed 'through interaction with a broad manifold, organic and inorganic. There is no completely isolatable I, no isolatable social unit' (Pavo 17). Arne Naess' philosophy exhorts every human being to reach Self- Realization. The term 'self' can be interpreted in three ways; ego, self and Self. The ego can be understood as a self that primarily concerns itself with fulfilling the biological or bodily needs of a person. Thus, it is a narrow selfish self. On the other hand, what encompasses more is the 'self'. The self does not limit itself to the needs of the body but extends itself by reaching out to others. It accomplishes by caring for the well-being of the immediate family and closest of friends. More encompassing than the self, however is the 'Self'. The 'Self' embraces all entities or all life forms. What the Self entails is that it seeks to care for the well-being of the whole of the environment (Pavo 17). Arne Naess calls the movement that upholds Ecosophy T as Deep Ecology Movement. He explains that the 'distinctive aspects of the Deep Ecology Movement were its recognition the inherent value of all other living beings and the use of this view in shaping environmental policies' (Drengson 3).

Before the spread of Arne Naess' Ecosophy T, the Khasis have already seen the inherent worth of every organic and inorganic being. But the systematized Ecosophy T helps one to understand the worldview of the Khasis better. Every view of the Khasis towards the environment is an identification with a larger self. A Khasi has the capacity to extend his/ her identity to plants, animals, rivers, hills, fire, water, wind, sun, moon etc. The process to Self-realization is guided by the tenet *Tip Briew-Tip Blei* or 'Know Man Know God'. For a Khasi respect to human beings precedes respect to God. A tangible helps him/her to understand the

intangible. First, a Khasi learns to respect his/her fellow beings and then he/she respects the environment and when he/she respects the two, he/she learns to respect God.

The Khasis identify themselves with another animate or inanimate being by delving into its pain and suffering. They can associate their feelings with other non-human beings from the experiences they have with their fellow beings. These experiences have transformed them to be more humane. Khasi folk narratives are proofs of their inclusiveness, identification and empathy towards non-humans. The narrative *The Animal Dance Festival* depicts the kindness of the Khasis to a *Lynx*. The narrative is about the animals holding a dancing festival. During the dance *Thunder* enjoys the limelight but after the entry of *Lynx* bringing with him a sword that arrests the attention of all animals, *Thunder* feels insecure and tricks *Lynx* by borrowing the sword, promising to return after the dance. After the dance, *Thunder* does not return the sword, instead, he carries it with him to his abode. *Lynx* feels betrayed and attempts since then to go to the abode of the *Thunder* by digging a hole in the ground and living in it. He never wanders far from his home and raises a mound everyday so that one day it would touch the sky and he would rightfully take his sword back from *Thunder*. The *Hynniew Trep*, who witness the unfair treatment done on *Lynx*, never disturb his habitat. Empathy for *Lynx* is a kind of inclusion that the world is one family.

The respect for habitat of animals is deep seated in every memory of the Khasis. For instance, trees are more than living things. They are books etched with stories. A particular tree *Dienglieng*, *Betula Acuminata*, is not to be cut for fuel or for making houses. The reason is that it reminds the Khasis of the tragedy of a girl. According to the narrative *Dienglieng*, a mother leaves her infant daughter at home while she goes to the market. An eagle stalks the baby and carries her away and raises her as her child in the nest that rested on a tree *Betula Acuminata*. The infant grows up into a lovely girl and loves the eagle as her own parent. Later on, people spot the girl on a branch of the tree and capture her. On returning the girl to the human parents the girl feels like a fish out of water and longs to go back to the eagle. One day when the girl is taken care by her grandmother, the eagle tries to carry her away but the effort is futile. Eventually, the girl asks the eagle to open its mouth and swallow her to which the eagle agrees and both die in this attempt. Witnessing the unfortunate incident, the Khasis buried them with proper rites and refrained from cutting the tree on which the nest of the eagle and the girl lay. The tree is a reminder that great love exists between the eagle and the girl.

Love for animals is etched in the hearts of the Khasis. It is evidential through their treatment of dogs. The legend *Ka Iew Luri Lura* depicts Khasi compassion for the dog. The legend tells that in the ancient days the dog lived in the jungle. A fair was held and all the animals were supposed to fetch an item to the fair for selling. A dog found a package of *tungrymbai* or 'fermented beans' left by a human on the way to the market. He wrapped it carefully and displayed it in the fair. On being asked by other animals he opened the leaf package and pungent smell arose. Disgusted with the smell, all the animals stomped the

tungrymbai and chased the dog away from the fair. The dog searched for shelter and pleaded with a man to have mercy on him. The Khasi felt sorry for the dog's misadventure and allowed him to stay in his verandah. Thus, the dog came to live with the Khasi people.

Although the Khasis were introduced to formal education only after the arrival of Thomas Jones, the Welsh Presbyterian missionary, in the year 1842, yet they already learnt how to be kind to all the creatures in and around them. Before 1842, oral tradition was used to pass on knowledge and information. The Khasis do not have their own script but use the Roman script introduced by Thomas Jones. But absence of alphabets cannot be the parameter for judging them. Nongkynrih writes, before the Whites came, they were 'not a band of barbarians roving the hills for heads and scalps. They did not live up trees like monkeys, nor hunt for food like savages' (vii). They knew how to till the land for cultivation. They engaged themselves in weaving, handicraft, iron smelting, trade and commerce. They conducted themselves with propriety towards humans and non-humans. Who was their teacher then? It was nature. Miri writes

Nature for a Khasi is like a book. The teaching and wisdom he derives from it, he makes use of in his daily life. He examines meticulously, and with great care the objects around him. He cares for and treasures all he sees and observes so that they could be of help to him in all his needs. Nature is also like a big hospital on whose threshold all types of medicine and reason complement one another and a Khasi is not thus helpless. He lives peacefully in his own land and enjoys the embrace of nature (105).

For the Khasis, a forest is more than a cluster of trees. It is like a book that records their experience. The Khasis regard every species in the forest with proper conduct. For instance, when a Khasi hears the cuckoo of a *langbyrku* or the green pigeon, he/she is reminded of the unfortunate incident of the two sisters who metamorphosed into birds. The two sisters had a mean and cruel stepfather. More often than not they received beatings from him and were made to sleep on empty stomachs. Brooding on their pathetic state they saw the hens pecking on the grains of rice falling down from the wooden mortar in which they were pounding. They plucked the feathers, implanted them on their arms and attempted flying. When they learnt flying, they flew to the deepest part of the forest vowing never to return to their parents. They also vowed never to touch the ground, inhibiting themselves from remembering the unjust treatment that was meted out to them by the parents.

However, there are actions of the *Hynniew trep* that may seem anthropocentric. Anthropocentrism is the belief that man is the centre of the universe and the measure of all things. It is a diametrical opposite of ecocentrism. It has a negative connotation and is an analogy with egocentrism. Morally, it is wrong to be self-centred in the individual case and in the same way it is also morally wrong to be human-centred in the collective case. The first action can be traced back to the time when the *Hynniew Trep* chopped off the *Diengiei* tree

because it was growing to a monstrous height and width, overshadowing the earth. Another incident is the cutting of the tiger's tongue because it helped the *Diengiei* tree grow. In my opinion, a justification can be made that these actions are not anthropocentric but human-centric.

It is unavoidable for the *Hynniew Trep* not to think as humans. Their view is shaped and limited because of the position they are placed in. They regard themselves to be at the centre of the universe, and any creature anywhere else would have the same perspective for themselves. Thus, it is inescapable for the *Hynniew Trep* to think as humans. Ferre calls this 'perspectival anthropocentrism' (Hayward 51). Every species has their own legitimate interests to pursue. But if these interests are detrimental to other species, it will not preclude those who are affected by to safeguard themselves. The *Hynniew Trep*, like all other species, have their own interests to pursue and their human-centric is unobjectionable. The monstrous growth of the *Diengiei* caused darkness to creep to every part of the earth and along with it evil. The licking of the tiger at the *Diengiei* made it recover from its wound. These occurrences are detrimental to the peaceful existence of other creatures. Therefore, it is unavoidable and unobjectionable for the *Hynniew Trep* to cut the tree or maim the tiger. Nevertheless "anthropocentrism cannot simply be equated with human-centredness if it is to perform the critical function envisaged for it, since there are also respects in which human-centredness is unavoidable, unobjectionable or even desirable" (Hayward 51).

The cutting of the tree or maiming the tiger puts one in a position to ask whether these actions tantamount to speciesism or not? Speciesism is arbitrary discrimination on the basis of species. It is a term coined in analogy with sexism and racism (Hayward 52). I opine that these actions do not amount to speciesism either because the preferential consideration was undertaken for non-arbitrary reason. The felling of the *Diengiei* and maiming the tiger were done so as to bring sunlight to the world again which is the greater good. The *Hynniew Trep* can be accused of speciesism only if they give preference of their own interests over other species for morally arbitrary reasons.

If an inherent worth is seen in every creature, perplexity arises and questions pop up such as does Ecosophy entail the reality that nobody is allowed to kill any creature because all creatures have values? Naess opines that killing or death is part of the natural process in the environment. He reiterates that killing is unavoidable only if it is justified. He proposes the *Hunter and Bear Dialogue* as a guide" The Hunter has a long discussion with the spirit of the bear, and explains apologetically that the larder is bare and that he must now kill the bear to nourish his family. In return, the hunter reminds the bear's spirit that both he and his family will die one day, and turn to dust, and so to vegetation, sustenance for the descendants of the bear" (19).

Over the years, the Khasis attitude towards nature has undergone changes. Meghalaya attained separate statehood status in 1972. In the name of development, social reality changed.

Just fifty years before people relied on forests and agriculture but when the government was formed development began to take place- urbanization was the key. Technological intervention, connected roads mushroomed at a very fast pace. Everyone is brainwashed that personal prosperity is a priority. This attitude is conspicuous in certain parts of the Khasi hills today. Hills that were clothed with pines are now barren. The transition of nature is depicted in the poem *Kynshi* by Kynpham Sing Nongkynrih. The poet initially eulogises the place but later changes his tone. He is disturbed by the indiscriminate felling of trees in this region (43).

Presently, the Khasis are losing grip on the ancient past. Christianity and the government are the two entities that people are flocking to. But with the rise of environmentalism, folkloristics, social groups, writers and researchers a revival of faith in the ancient *U Hynniew Trep- U Hynniew Skum*; Khasi Ecosophy, is gradually seeping into the consciousness of the present day Khasis, allowing the comeback of the world as one family.

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